

An LMI approach to Mixed H_∞/H_- fault detection observer design for linear fractional-order systems

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the problem of robust fault detection for linear time-invariant fractional-order systems (FOSs) assumed to be affected by sensor, actuator and process faults as well as disturbances. The observer-based method was employed to solve the problem, where the detector is an observer. The problem was transformed into the mixed H_∞/H_- robust optimization problem to make the system disturbance-resistant on one hand and fault-sensitive on the other hand. Then, sufficient conditions were obtained to solve the problem in the linear matrix inequality (LMI) mode. Finally, the effectiveness and superiority of the method were demonstrated by simulating the solutions on a single-input multi-output thermal testing bench.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fraction calculations made their way through engineering and application after 300 years and merely theoretical studies in mathematics [1]-[18]. Given different and new mathematics provided in fraction calculations, debates in various fields such as control theory require new proofs and theorems. As a result, the fundamental aspects of fractional-order systems (FOSs) were investigated, and stability theorems were proposed [19]-[22]. However, many aspects remain open, with some of them being currently studied. One of such aspects is fault detection (FD) in FOSs, which is of great importance. According to searches, there have been few studies in this area. Aribi *et al.* [23] present three methods to evaluate fractional residual. Aribi *et al.* [24], diagnosis methods in FO thermal systems have been proposed. The FD control of FOSs is investigated in [25]. Zhong *et al.* [26] tried to find a way to solve the fault detection observer design problem for fractional-order systems. Their subject is precisely the same as the subject of this article. However, they were utterly unsuccessful because they could not prove the stability of the closed-loop system, and the published article has very undeniable flaws.

Various methods have been proposed to detect faults [27]-[33]. One of these methods is the model-based FD technique, which has been practically employed in many industrial applications [34]-[38]. Figure 1 illustrates the algorithm of the model-based FD method. Disturbances disable typical fault detection systems in real-life systems since they are treated as faults. So, alarms are activated while there has been no fault in

the system. For this reason, robust fault detection systems have been designed. In a fault detection system, robustness is defined as the system’s sensitivity to faults and resistance against unknown inputs [39]-[42].

The main challenge is now to implement the model-based fault detection algorithm on FOSs and make the system disturbance-resistant on the one hand and fault-sensitive on the other hand. Additionally, it is well-known that the use of linear matrix inequality (LMI) can eliminate restrictions on conventional approaches, and can be used to solve problems involving multiple matrix variables. Besides those, different structures can be imposed on these matrices [43]-[46]. To this end, the problem was transformed into the mixed H_∞/H_- robust optimization problem, also present the results in linear matrix inequalities (LMIs) robust control theoretical framework.

Figure 1. Model-based fault diagnosis algorithm

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In section 2, implementation of the model-based technique on the FOS, as well as, the preliminaries and the problem statement are given. The solutions to the FD problem for FOSs are presented in section 3. Also, some simulation examples are given in section 5 to illustrate the results. Finally, some concluding remarks are provided in section 6. Notations: A^T denoted the transpose of a matrix A , its conjugate \bar{A} and its conjugate transpose A^* . $Her(A)$ is short for $A + A^*$, and $\sigma_{max}(A)$ represents the maximum singular value of A .

2. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider the following FOS:

$$G: \begin{cases} D^\alpha x(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + B_d d(t) + B_f f(t) \\ y(t) = Cx(t) + Du(t) + D_d d(t) + D_f f(t) \\ x(t) = x(0) \quad t \in [-h_1, 0] \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

System G is the state space form of a time-invariant linear FOS where D is the differ-integral operator and $0 < \alpha < 1$. $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the pseudo-state vector. $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$ denotes the measured output. $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_d \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$, $B_f \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times q}$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n}$, $D_d \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times p}$ and $D_f \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times q}$ are constant matrices. The $x(0)$, stand for initial condition defined on $[-h_1, 0]$ where $h_1 \in \mathbb{R}$ and $0 < h_1$. This FOS affected by disturbance $d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ as an unwanted input and fault $f(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$ input as a bug in the system. If there is a problem in reading and sending data, or in measurement, it is referred to as a sensor fault $f_s(t)$, which is represented by considering $B_f = I$ in the output equation of the system as (2) [47].

$$y(t) = Cx(t) + D_d d(t) + f_s(t) \tag{2}$$

If there is a problem with actuators' performance, it affects the input of the system and calls it an actuator fault f_A :

$$\begin{aligned} D^\alpha x(t) &= A x(t) + B(u(t) + f_A(t)) + B_d d(t) \\ y(t) &= C x(t) + D(u(t) + f_A(t)) + D_d d(t) \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

by adding the process fault $f_p(t)$ according to its location and type and considering $B_f = B_p$ and $D_f = D_p$, generally, in this method, additive faults for describing the fault is considered for the system with sensor, actuator and process faults. As a result, the faults can be rewritten as:

$$f(t) = \begin{bmatrix} f_A(t) \\ f_p(t) \\ f_s(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad B_f = [B \quad B_p \quad 0], \quad D_f = [D \quad D_p \quad I],$$

one of the best definitions of fractional derivatives so far in control applications is the Caputo's definition [48]:

$${}_a D_t^\alpha \triangleq \frac{1}{\Gamma(k-\alpha)} \int_a^t \frac{f^{(k)}(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^{\alpha+1-k}} d\tau \quad (4)$$

if the FOS (1) is relaxed at $t = 0$, the transfer functions of the system, in which the fault and disturbance are as inputs and the output of the system considered as output are as (5) and (6), respectively [49]:

$$G_{yf}(s) = C(S^\alpha I - A)^{-1} B_f + D_f \quad (5)$$

$$G_{yd}(s) = C(S^\alpha I - A)^{-1} B_d + D_d \quad (6)$$

according to Figure 1, after determining the dynamical equations of the system with the fault, the next important step is to define a stable observer for the system (1). For this purpose, the observer F has been designed as (7).

$$F: \begin{cases} D^\alpha \hat{x}(t) = A \hat{x}(t) + L r(t) \\ \hat{y}(t) = C \hat{x}(t) \\ r(t) = y(t) - \hat{y}(t) \\ \hat{x}(t) = \varphi(t) \quad t \in [-h_2, 0] \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Where $\hat{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the detection observer state vector, $\hat{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$ represents the output estimation vectors, $r(t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$ is residual, and $L \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ is the observer gain.

By the combination of the filter (7), the system (1) and considering $e(t) = x(t) - \hat{x}(t)$ the following augmented FOS is obtained:

$$\begin{cases} D^\alpha e(t) = (A - LC)e(t) + (B_d - LD_d)d(t) + (B_f - LD_f)f(t) \\ r(t) = Ce(t) + D_d d(t) + D_f f(t) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

To have a robust FD system, the design should be carried out in such a way that the following conditions are established:

- The observer (7) must be designed such that asymptotically stability of the augmented system (8) is guaranteed. To achieve this condition, $\left| \text{Arg} \left(\text{spec}((A - LC)) \right) \right| > \alpha \frac{\pi}{2}$, where $\text{spec}((A - LC))$ is the set of eigenvalues of $(A - LC)$ or there exist $P > 0$ and $Q > 0$ such that $\text{sym}(rAP + \bar{r}AQ) < 0$ where $r = e^{j(1-\alpha)\frac{\pi}{2}}$ is asymptotically stable [50]. Figure 2 shows the stability region for this system.
- Robustness to disturbance input is one of the main design points of the FD. By using H_∞ optimization criteria, this performance index expressed as (9) [51].

$$\sup \frac{\|r(t)\|_2}{\|d(t)\|_2} < \gamma, \gamma > 0 \quad (9)$$

- Robust control by H_- optimizations criteria is the best idea for solving system sensitivity to faults. Performance index (10) guarantees the residual's sensitivity to faults, which is expressed as (10) [52].

$$\sup \frac{\|r(t)\|_2}{\|f(t)\|_2} > \beta, \beta > 0 \quad (10)$$

Figure 2. Stable region illustration

Based on the three above assumptions, mixing H_∞/H_- is the proposed method in this work for FDI design. The following definitions and lemmas are used for implementing the proposed method. Definition 1. [53] The H_∞ norm of $G_{yd}(s)$ for FOS (1) is defined as (11).

$$\|G_{yd}\|_{(H_\infty)} \triangleq \sup_{Re(s) \geq 0} \sigma_{max}(G_{yd}(s)) \tag{11}$$

Lemma 1: (H -BR): [54] Consider the FOS (1) and $G_{yu}(s) = C(S^\alpha I - A)^{-1}B + D$ then $\|G_{yu}(s)\|_{H_\infty} < \gamma$ if only if there exist $P > 0$ and $Q > 0$ such that:

$$\begin{bmatrix} sym(AX) & * & * \\ CX & -\gamma I & * \\ B^T & D^T & -\gamma I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \tag{12}$$

where $X = \begin{cases} e^{j\theta} P + e^{-j\theta} Q, & \text{if } 0 < \alpha < 1 \\ e^{j\theta} & \text{if } 1 \leq \alpha < 1 \end{cases}$ $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}(1 - \alpha)$

Lemma 2: [55] Let matrices $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $\Phi \in H_2$, $\Theta \in H_{(n+m)}$ and $\Psi \in H_2$. Set Λ is defined as (13).

$$\Lambda(\Phi, \Psi) \triangleq \left\{ \lambda \in C \left[\begin{matrix} \lambda \\ I \end{matrix} \right]^* \Phi \begin{bmatrix} \lambda \\ I \end{bmatrix} = 0, \begin{bmatrix} \lambda \\ I \end{matrix} \right]^* \Psi \begin{bmatrix} \lambda \\ I \end{bmatrix} \geq 0 \right\} \tag{13}$$

For $H(\lambda) \triangleq (\lambda I_n - A)^{-1}$, there holds:

$$\begin{bmatrix} H(\lambda) \\ I_m \end{bmatrix}^* \Theta \begin{bmatrix} H(\lambda) \\ I_m \end{bmatrix} < 0, \quad \forall \lambda \in \Lambda \tag{14}$$

there exist $P, Q \in H_n$ and $Q > 0$ such that:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ I_n & 0 \end{bmatrix}^* (\Phi \otimes P + \Psi \otimes Q) \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ I_n & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \Theta < 0 \tag{15}$$

then "(15) \implies (14)". Furthermore, if Λ represents a curve in the complex plane, then holds "(15) \iff (14)".

Lemma 3: [55] The set $\Lambda(\Phi, \Psi)$ is defined as:

$$\Lambda(\Phi, \Psi) \triangleq \left\{ \lambda \in C \left[\begin{matrix} \lambda \\ I \end{matrix} \right]^* \Phi \begin{bmatrix} \lambda \\ I \end{bmatrix} \geq 0, \begin{bmatrix} \lambda \\ I \end{matrix} \right]^* \Psi \begin{bmatrix} \lambda \\ I \end{bmatrix} \geq 0 \right\} \tag{16}$$

if matrices $P > 0$ and $Q > 0$ exist such that LMI condition (15) holds, then condition (14) holds $\forall \lambda \in \Lambda$.

Lemma 4: (Projection lemma) [56]. Unstructured matrix X satisfies the following equations if a symmetric matrix $Z \in S_m$ and column dimension m , U and V matrices exist:

$$U^T X V + V^T X^T U + Z < 0 \quad (17)$$

if and only if:

$$N_U^T Z N_U < 0 \quad (18)$$

and

$$N_V^T Z N_V < 0 \quad (19)$$

concerning to X are satisfied. Where N_U and N_V are arbitrary matrices, whose columns form a basis of the null spaces of U and V , respectively.

Lemma 5: [57]. The FOS $G(s)$ is stable if and only if $\|G(s)\|_{H_\infty}$ is bounded.

3. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, conditions ii and iii are transformed into LMIs. Corollary 1 unifies the theorems. Theorem 1. The system (8) is stable, and the performance indices (9) is guaranteed, if there exist positive scalar γ positive definite symmetric matrices P_1 , Q_1 and matrices X , N such that the following LMIs hold:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{Her}(\Pi) + C^T C & \Xi_2 & \Omega + C^T D_d \\ * & -\lambda(X + X^T) & \lambda\Omega \\ * & * & D_d^T D_d - \gamma^2 I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (20)$$

where

$$\Pi = A^T X - C^T N^T, \Omega = X^T B_d - N D_d, \lambda > 0, \Xi_2 = \lambda \Pi - X^T + \bar{r} P_1 + r Q_1, r = e^{j\theta}, \theta = (1 - \alpha) \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

holds and the filter gain L is obtained:

$$L = X^{-T} N \quad (21)$$

Proof: Based on definition 1:

$$\|G(s)_{rd}\|_{H_\infty} \triangleq \sup_{\text{Re}(s) \geq 0} \bar{\sigma}(G(s)_{rd}) = \sup_{\text{Re}(s) \geq 0} \bar{\sigma}(C(S^\alpha I - \tilde{A})^{-1} \tilde{B}_d + D_d) \quad (22)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{A} &= A - LC \\ \tilde{B}_d &= B_d - LD_d \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

by some basic matrix calculations:

$$\|G(s)_{rd}\|_{H_\infty} < \gamma \Leftrightarrow G(s)_{rd} G(s)_{rd}^* - \gamma^2 I < 0 \quad \forall \text{Re}(s) \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} H(\lambda) \\ I_m \end{bmatrix}^* \Theta \begin{bmatrix} H(\lambda) \\ I_m \end{bmatrix} < 0, \quad \forall \lambda \in \Lambda \quad (24)$$

where $H(\lambda) \triangleq (\lambda I_n - \tilde{A})^{-1}$, $\lambda = S^\alpha$, and $\Lambda(\Phi, \Psi)$ is defined in (13), also:

$$\Theta = \begin{bmatrix} C^T C & C^T D_d \\ D_d^T C & D_d^T D_d - \gamma^2 I \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

then according to Lemma 2, the last part of (24) is also equivalent to the statement that $\exists P_1, Q_1 \in H_n$, $P_1 > 0$ and $Q_1 > 0$ such that the LMI (24) holds.

$$\begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ \tilde{A} & \tilde{B}_d \end{bmatrix}^T (\Phi \otimes P_1 + \Psi \otimes Q_1) \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ \tilde{A} & \tilde{B}_d \end{bmatrix} + \Theta < 0 \quad (26)$$

similar to [54],

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \bar{r} \\ r & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \Psi &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & r \\ \bar{r} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

now the inequality (26) can be reformulated as $N_U^T Z N_U < 0$ where N_U and Z are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} Z &= \begin{bmatrix} C^T C & \bar{r} P_1 + r Q_1 & C^T D_d \\ r P_1 + \bar{r} Q_1 & 0 & 0 \\ D_d^T C & 0 & D_d^T D_d - \gamma^2 I \end{bmatrix} \\ N_U &= \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ \tilde{A} & \tilde{B}_d \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

by defining the matrices N_V and V as (29).

$$N_V = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda I & 0 \\ -I & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow V = [I \quad \lambda I \quad 0] \tag{29}$$

It can be obtained by Lemma 4 that inequality $N_U^T Z N_U < 0$ is equivalent to:

$$Z + \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{A}^T \\ -I \\ \tilde{B}_d \end{bmatrix} [X \quad \lambda X \quad 0] + \begin{bmatrix} X^T \\ \lambda X^T \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} [\tilde{A}^T \quad -I \quad \tilde{B}_d] < 0 \tag{30}$$

Now by substituting $N = X^T L$ inequality (20) is obtained, and the proof is completed.

Theorem 2. The augmented fractional-order system (8) is stable and it guarantees the performance index (10), if there exist positive scalar $\beta > 0$ and symmetric matrices P_2, Q_2 and matrices X, N such that the following LMI:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Her(\Pi) - C^T C & \Xi_2 & \Omega - C^T D_f \\ * & \lambda(X - X^T) & \lambda \Omega \\ * & * & -D_f^T D_f + \beta^2 I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \tag{31}$$

where

$$\Pi = A^T X - C^T N^T, \Omega = X^T B_f - N D_f, \lambda > 0, \Xi_2 = \lambda \Pi - X^T + \bar{r} P_2 + r Q_2, r = e^{j\theta}, \theta = (1 - \alpha) \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

The filter gain L is given by (21).

Proof: Although the principles of proving this theorem are very similar to that Theorem 1, since it contains small and essential points, the proof of this theorem is fully addressed.

Based on definition 1:

$$\|G(s)_{rf}\|_{H_\infty} \triangleq \sup_{Re(s) \geq 0} \bar{\sigma}(G(s)_{rf}) = \sup_{Re(s) \geq 0} \bar{\sigma}(C(S^\alpha I - \tilde{A})^{-1} \tilde{B}_f + D_f) \tag{32}$$

where $\tilde{B}_f = B_f - L D_f$,

By analyzing $\|G(s)_{rf}\|_{H_\infty}$:

$$\|G(s)_{rf}\|_{H_\infty} < \gamma \Leftrightarrow G(s)_{rf} G(s)_{rf}^* - \gamma^2 I < 0 \quad \forall Re(s) \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} H(\lambda) \\ I_m \end{bmatrix}^* \Theta \begin{bmatrix} H(\lambda) \\ I_m \end{bmatrix} < 0, \forall \lambda \in \Lambda \tag{33}$$

where $H(\lambda) \triangleq (\lambda I_n - \tilde{A})^{-1} \tilde{B}_f$ and $\Lambda(\Phi, \Psi)$ is defined in (11), also:

$$\Theta = \begin{bmatrix} -C^T C & -C^T D_f \\ -D_f^T C & D_f^T D_f - \beta^2 I \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

then according to Lemma 3, the last part of (29) is also equivalent to the statement that $\exists P_2, Q_2 \in H_n, P_2 > 0$ and $Q_1 > 0$ such that the LMI (29) holds.

$$\begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ \tilde{A} & \tilde{B}_f \end{bmatrix}^T (\Phi \otimes P_2 + \Psi \otimes Q_2) \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ \tilde{A} & \tilde{B}_f \end{bmatrix} + \Theta < 0 \quad (35)$$

similar to [54],

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \bar{r} \\ r & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \Psi &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & r \\ \bar{r} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

now the inequality (29) can be reformulated as $N_U^T Z N_U < 0$ where N_U and Z are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} Z &= \begin{bmatrix} -C^T C & \bar{r}P_2 + rQ_2 & -C^T D_f \\ rP_1 + \bar{r}Q_1 & 0 & 0 \\ -D_f^T C & 0 & D_f^T D_f - \beta^2 I \end{bmatrix} \\ N_U &= \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ \tilde{A} & \tilde{B}_f \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

by defining the matrices N_V and V as (38).

$$N_V = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda I & 0 \\ -I & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow V = [I \quad \lambda I \quad 0] \quad (38)$$

It can be obtained by Lemma 4 that inequality $N_U^T Z N_U < 0$ is equivalent to:

$$Z + \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{A}^T \\ -I \\ \tilde{B}_f^T \end{bmatrix} [X \quad \lambda X \quad 0] + \begin{bmatrix} X^T \\ \lambda X^T \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} [\tilde{A}^T \quad -I \quad \tilde{B}_f^T] < 0 \quad (39)$$

Now by substituting $N = X^T L$ inequality (31) is obtained, and the proof is completed.

Corollary 1. Solving the following convex optimization problem, results a feasible solution to the multi-objective H_-/H_∞ problem (fault detection problem) for Given:

$$\begin{aligned} \max & \quad \beta \\ X, P_1, P_2, Q_1, Q_2, N & \\ s. t & \quad (20), (31). \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

Proof: By collecting the theorems 1 and 2, the proof is completed.

Remark 3: In this work, the residual evaluation function is defined as [52]:

$$J(t) = \left(\theta^{-1} \int_0^\theta r^T(s)r(s)ds \right)^{1/2} \quad (41)$$

where θ represents the detection time range. The upper threshold values are calculated as:

$$J_{th} = \sup_{\substack{f(t)=0 \\ d(t) \in L_2}} J(t) \quad (42)$$

4. SIMULATION EXAMPLES

The model considered for validating the results proved in this article is the testing bench that

described in [24]. As can be seen in Figure 3, this type of test bench made up of two long aluminum rods which are glued together with the heat paste. The input of this model, which is a single input multi output system is voltage $V_r(t)$ and its outputs are θ_1 , θ_2 , θ_3 and θ_4 . Rod 1 thermal behavior is as (43) and (44).

$$\theta_1 = \mathcal{L}^{-1}[G_{13}] * \theta_3 \quad (43)$$

$$\theta_3 = \mathcal{L}^{-1}[G_{V3}] * V_r(t) \quad (44)$$

Figure 3. Two rods thermal bench

Rod 2 thermal behavior is as (45) and (46).

$$\theta_2 = \mathcal{L}^{-1}[G_{42}] * \theta_4 \quad (45)$$

$$\theta_4 = \mathcal{L}^{-1}[G_{V4}] * V_r(t) \quad (46)$$

Where numerical values of identified transfer functions are:

$$G_{V3}(s) = \frac{-348.5s^{0.5} + 319.9}{1840s^{1.5} - 130s + 485.7s^{0.5} + 1} = \frac{b_1^{V3}s^{0.5} + b_0^{V3}}{a_3^{V3}s^{1.5} + a_2^{V3}s + a_1^{V3}s^{0.5} + a_0^{V3}} \quad (47)$$

$$G_{31}(s) = \frac{1.1587}{2.367s^{0.5} + 1} - 0.1599 = \frac{b_0^{31}}{a_1^{31}s^{0.5} + a_0^{31}} + D_{31} \quad (48)$$

$$G_{V4}(s) = \frac{-299.5s^{0.5} + 260.7}{6472s^{1.5} - 300.2s + 453.2s^{0.5} + 1} = \frac{b_1^{V4}s^{0.5} + b_0^{V4}}{a_3^{V4}s^{1.5} + a_2^{V4}s + a_1^{V4}s^{0.5} + a_0^{V4}} \quad (49)$$

$$G_{42}(s) = \frac{1.6361}{0.5415s^{0.5} + 1} - 0.6372 = \frac{b_0^{42}}{a_1^{42}s^{0.5} + a_0^{42}} + D_{42} \quad (50)$$

Observability forms of fractional order transmittances (47)-(50) are:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} D^\alpha \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_1(t) \\ \zeta_2(t) \\ \theta_3(t) \end{bmatrix} = A_{V3} \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_1(t) \\ \zeta_2(t) \\ \theta_3(t) \end{bmatrix} + B_{V3} V_r(t) \\ \theta_3(t) = C_{V3} \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_1(t) \\ \zeta_2(t) \\ \theta_3(t) \end{bmatrix} \end{array} \right. \quad (51)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} D^\alpha \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_4(t) \\ \zeta_5(t) \\ \theta_4(t) \end{bmatrix} = A_{V4} \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_4(t) \\ \zeta_5(t) \\ \theta_4(t) \end{bmatrix} + B_{V4} V_r(t) \\ \theta_4(t) = C_{V4} \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_4(t) \\ \zeta_5(t) \\ \theta_4(t) \end{bmatrix} \end{array} \right. \quad (52)$$

$$\begin{cases} D^\alpha \zeta_3(t) = \frac{-a_0^{31}}{a_1^{31}} \zeta_3(t) + \frac{b_0^{31}}{a_1^{31}} \theta_3(t) = A_{31} \zeta_3(t) + B_{31} \theta_3(t) \\ \theta_1(t) = \zeta_3(t) + D_{31} \theta_3(t) \end{cases} \quad (53)$$

$$\begin{cases} D^\alpha \zeta_6(t) = \frac{-a_0^{42}}{a_1^{42}} \zeta_6(t) + \frac{b_0^{42}}{a_1^{42}} \theta_4(t) = A_{42} \zeta_6(t) + B_{42} \theta_4(t) \\ \theta_2(t) = \zeta_6(t) + D_{42} \theta_4(t) \end{cases} \quad (54)$$

where

$$A_{Vi} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \frac{-a_0^{Vi}}{a_3^{Vi}} \\ 1 & 0 & \frac{-a_1^{Vi}}{a_3^{Vi}} \\ 0 & 1 & \frac{-a_1^{Vi}}{a_3^{Vi}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad B_{Vi} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{b_0^{Vi}}{b_3^{Vi}} \\ \frac{b_1^{Vi}}{b_3^{Vi}} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad C_{Vi} = [0 \quad 0 \quad 1]; \quad i = 3,4. \quad (55)$$

the pseudo state space description of this SIMO system is as (56):

$$\begin{cases} D^\alpha x(t) = A x(t) + B u(t) \\ y(t) = C x(t) + D u(t) \end{cases} \quad (56)$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} A_{V3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ B_{31}C_{V3} & A_{31} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{V4} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{42}C_{V4} & A_{42} \end{bmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} B_{V3} \\ 0 \\ B_{V4} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} D_{31}C_{V3} & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{V3} & 0 & D_{41}C_{V4} & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{V4} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad D = 0.$$

$$x(t) = [\zeta_1(t) \quad \zeta_2(t) \quad \theta_3(t) \quad \zeta_3(t) \quad \zeta_4(t) \quad \zeta_5(t) \quad \theta_4(t) \quad \zeta_6(t)]$$

$$y(t) = [\theta_1(t) \quad \theta_2(t) \quad \theta_3(t) \quad \theta_4(t)]$$

Consider the FOS (1) with the following parameters:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -0.0005 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -0.2640 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.0707 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.4895 & -0.4225 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0002 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -0.0700 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.0464 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 3.0214 & -1.8467 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B = 0, \quad B_d = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B_f = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$D = 0, \quad D_d = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad D_f = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -0.1599 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.6372 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$d(t) = 0.5 \exp(-0.4t) \cos(0.7\pi t) u(t).$$

The fault signal $f(t)$ is simulated as a square wave of unit amplitude from 40 to 60 steps. For a given $\gamma = 0.0328$, we solved the optimization problem Corollary 1 by YALMIP toolbox in Matlab and β is obtained as 71.8540. Furthermore, the observer gains were obtained as:

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0011 & 0 & 2.1735 & 0 \\ 0.0012 & 0 & 3.2501 & 0 \\ -0.0009 & 0 & 2.9924 & 0 \\ -0.0040 & 0 & 0.2422 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.0010 & 0 & 0.9972 \\ 0 & 0.0002 & 0 & 2.5353 \\ 0 & 0.0043 & 0 & 2.6462 \\ 0 & -0.8542 & 0 & 3.5680 \end{bmatrix}$$

Real and estimated outputs are represented in Figures 4-7. The threshold values of residual signal r_1 and r_3 computed by (42) as $J_{thr1} = 0.0908$ and $J_{thr3} = -0.00021620$. Residuals in the faulty cases are shown in Figures 8 and 9. It can be concluded that the robustness against disturbance and the fault sensitivity are both amplified, and the fault is well separated from disturbance.

Figure 4. The output θ_1 and its estimate

Figure 5. The output θ_2 and its estimate

Figure 6. The output θ_3 and its estimate

Figure 7. The output θ_4 and its estimate

Figure 9. Residual signal r_3

Aribi *et al.* [24] performed the simulation with the Luenberger diagnosis observer method without considering the effect of disturbance. Also, the overshoot at the beginning is a big drawback of that method. Their other methods, generalized dynamic parity space, are very good, although they do not introduce a disturbance signal.

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, the robust fault detection problem has been investigated for a linear time-invariant fractional-order system in the simultaneous presence of sensor, actuator and process faults as well as input and output disturbances. The core of this study is the formulation of the FD design problem as the mixed H_∞/H_- robust optimization problem to satisfy the fault sensitivity and disturbance attenuation. Furthermore, the linear matrix inequality approach has been introduced to warrant stability and the two multi-objective H_∞/H_- performances. Finally, the effectiveness of the proposed theory is validated via numerical results. In future work, this problem will be solved by considering other algorithms.

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